

TGICA-25 2.1

2016 Usage Report for the IPCC DDC - Supplementary

Document ownership and history		
Owner	CEDA for TGICA-24-W1 Supplementary Information	
Location	TGICA_IPCC-DDC_Usage_Dev_Countries.docx	
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Version	0.1	
Date	2017-05-04	
Version history		
Date	Version	Comment
2017-05-04	0.1	Initial report presented to TGICA co-chairs in response to request for further information about DDC usage in developing countries and economies in Transition

Table of Contents

1. Summary	1
2. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for Asia	2
3. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for Africa	5
4. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for South America	8
5. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for Central America	10
6. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for the Caribbean	12

1. Summary

This report presents annual statistics for the geographical distribution of user sessions for the IPCC-DDC web site <http://ipcc-data.org>.

The IPCC-DDC usage information is presented as a series of maps with corresponding data tables. Note that data for the Pacific Islands is presented as a data table only. The period covered is from January 1st 2009 to December 31st 2016. Geographical usage statistics are for developing countries and economies in transition in the Asia-Pacific region, Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean. In the context of this report developing countries and economies in transition are defined as those countries that are not Annex 1 parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.

The data is sourced from the Google Analytics service which monitors usage of the IPCC DDC. Only sessions which persist for longer than 10 seconds are included in the statistics for this report. The Google Analytics statistics have also been filtered to remove robotic and other automated behaviour.

2. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for Asia

Figure 1: Annual IPCC-DDC user sessions for Asia 2009-2016. Scale max = 2443.

East Asia Sessions	Year							
	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
China	1078	1225	1222	1074	1746	2060	1970	2304
South Korea	498	574	421	257	428	610	625	610
Taiwan	347	331	283	234	320	370	423	372
Hong Kong	90	112	104	114	133	152	203	231
Mongolia	10	11	4	15	28	17	11	11
Macau	6	6	9	2	6	3	6	7
Total	2671	2803	2547	2228	3401	3972	4089	4316

SE Asia Sessions	Year							
	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Thailand	324	253	371	265	335	507	531	401
Indonesia	183	139	145	197	244	332	310	331
Malaysia	90	147	90	100	176	249	260	254
Philippines	172	129	131	96	104	210	203	242
Vietnam	97	90	70	90	134	274	235	193
Singapore	159	95	146	127	274	160	173	173
Cambodia	2	6	9	14	28	36	41	50
Brunei		2	12	9	5	64	28	34
Myanmar	3	7		1	3	14	15	15
Laos	6	7	6	9	25	15	12	12
East Timor	1	25			1		3	
Total	1037	900	980	908	1329	1861	1811	1705

Pacific Island Sessions	Year							
	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Fiji	5	9	10	10	24	20	11	31
Papua New Guinea	9	2	1	1	3	5	3	2
New Caledonia	2	2	1	1	2	1	3	1
Solomon Islands					1	1	12	5
Vanuatu	2					1	3	1
Marshall Islands		1						2
Guam	2	3	2	1	1			1
Northern Mariana Islands								1
French Polynesia	1	1	1				2	5
Kiribati	5						1	
Tonga				1	1		1	
Samoa		3	1		4	5		
Micronesia					1			
Palau			1					
Total	26	21	17	14	37	33	36	49

South Asia Sessions	Year							
Country	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
India	975	1078	1131	1248	1756	2443	2389	2292
Iran	415	448	383	412	715	769	906	1602
Pakistan	48	73	50	85	119	190	232	205
Bangladesh	63	56	96	69	214	180	150	134
Nepal	38	61	74	69	84	117	174	120
Sri Lanka	45	61	40	30	73	62	80	59
Bhutan	2	2	4	5	9	10	11	8
Afghanistan	2	1			3	5	7	11
Maldives	3	2	1	1		4		
Total	1591	1782	1779	1919	2973	3780	3949	4431

West Asia Sessions	Year							
Country	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
United Arab Emirates	25	23	26	26	29	37	55	72
Israel	43	24	39	40	63	62	84	72
Saudi Arabia	17	24	19	35	65	68	61	58
Yemen	11	2	11	19	12	5	23	57
Iraq	3	6	10	4	22	34	42	48
Kuwait	8	6	3	4	1	4	11	26
Lebanon	23	9	18	11	12	32	41	26
Jordan	12	20	16	10	71	56	37	25
Qatar	4	7	5	2	12	17	9	20
Palestine	4	2	2	5	14	12	3	16
Oman	2	5	1	6	4	15	12	13
Georgia	20	10	4	25	15	3	8	12
Armenia	2	4	2	7	2	3	3	8
Azerbaijan	1	1	1	5	6	5	6	8
Syria	26	8	16	18	1	6	4	3
Bahrain	6	9	4	3	1	3	5	1
Total	351	287	294	348	532	629	680	692

Central Asia Sessions	Year							
Country	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Kazakhstan	12	14	9	7	11	12	32	58
Uzbekistan	1	4	2	10	2	7	7	9
Kyrgyzstan	4	2	4	4	4	12	8	7
Tajikistan		3	3	5	3	4	1	2
Turkmenistan				1			1	
Total	17	23	18	27	20	35	49	76

3. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for Africa

Figure 2: Annual IPCC-DDC user sessions for Africa 2009-2016. Scale max = 384.

Africa Sessions	Year							
Country	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
South Africa	288	230	181	200	232	301	375	294
Ethiopia	43	77	96	125	242	384	353	288
Kenya	38	58	85	79	95	165	210	187
Egypt	66	70	62	64	69	85	109	156
Nigeria	23	37	54	44	71	130	128	134
Morocco	31	33	25	26	52	97	86	111
Tunisia	70	32	15	26	41	61	56	69
Tanzania	12	25	23	20	77	90	80	45
Algeria	12	15	10	21	33	72	68	95
Ghana	10	17	12	31	22	53	60	64
Madagascar	9	12	10	16	17	30	70	40
Senegal	11	16	13	13	19	23	44	39
Uganda	15	14	23	15	32	30	41	35
Cameroon	5	16	9	20	21	24	50	30
Zimbabwe		8	13	26	37	24	40	42
Côte d'Ivoire	1	5	4	9	16	40	45	42
Sudan	3	22	5	6	14	9	18	37
Benin	8	7	10	9	27	11	18	35
Botswana	3	16	2	1	3	5	37	26
Mozambique	4	3	10	6	6	13	14	27
Libya	4		2	6	12	1	10	47
Zambia	5	3	2	6	1	6	27	20
Mauritius	7	11	15	19	11	16	13	9
Togo	1	1	2	14	18	20	9	13
Burkina Faso	8	3	19	4	3	10	1	17
Malawi		3	3	5	12	9	12	14
Niger	4	4	4	7	12	13	11	5
Namibia	2	1	5	1	12	12	15	7
Rwanda	3	8	1	7	3	16	7	3
Réunion	4	12	1	2	9	10	7	4
Mali	12		6		5	4	3	3
Angola		4			1	8	18	3
Swaziland	2	2		1	4	13	5	2
Congo-Kinshasa					5	4	8	7
Cape Verde	3			1	1	1	2	9
Lesotho		2	2	1	1	4	4	9
Gambia			1			7	3	5
Somalia						2	4	5
Comoros					1	3	8	2
Guinea-Bissau	1	2				5	1	1
Guinea						1		6
Mauritania			1			2	1	4
Congo-Brazzaville	1	3		1	2		1	1
Djibouti	2		1			1	1	

Liberia	2				2	3	1	1
Seychelles		1	1	1	1	1	2	
Burundi					4	4	1	
Sierra Leone						2	3	1
Eritrea							1	1
Gabon			2					1
Chad						1	2	
South Sudan						4		1
São Tomé & Príncipe						1		1
Mayotte							3	
Equatorial Guinea							1	
Total	713	773	730	833	1246	1831	2087	1998

4. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for South America

Figure 3: Annual IPCC-DDC User sessions for South America 2009-2016. Scale max = 862.

S America Sessions	Year							
Country	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Brazil	579	492	536	552	614	862	800	813
Colombia	98	127	140	154	229	281	336	315
Chile	94	77	111	97	151	126	227	201
Argentina	166	107	93	100	133	159	177	154
Peru	120	81	84	69	98	230	175	167
Ecuador	28	51	28	55	66	109	106	75
Venezuela	27	34	35	31	52	65	73	71
Bolivia	63	31	14	15	34	67	57	54
Uruguay	17	17	16	15	16	12	18	25
Guyana		4	1		1	6	10	8
Paraguay	7	2	3	9	8	8	8	14
French Guiana			1	2	4	2	4	
Suriname	1	2	1	4	6	6	4	18
Total	1200	1025	1063	1103	1412	1933	1995	1915

5. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for Central America

Figure 4: Annual IPCC-DDC User sessions for Central America 2009-2016. Scale max = 510.

C America Sessions	Year							
	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Mexico	339	342	273	268	437	510	470	448
Nicaragua	5	6	8	19	43	22	91	23
Panama	8	6	11	14	37	26	33	13
Costa Rica	50	33	22	26	31	60	47	62
Guatemala	10	9	17	6	27	17	28	28
Honduras	2	6	11	5	12	11	6	10
El Salvador	3	5	2	1	5	12	23	10
Belize			4	4	2	9	7	6
Total	417	407	348	343	594	667	705	600

6. IPCC-DDC User Sessions for the Caribbean

Figure 5: Annual IPCC-DDC User sessions for Caribbean 2009-2016.
Scale max = 60.

Caribbean Sessions	Year							
Country	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Trinidad & Tobago	38	19	20	18	21	19	28	55
Dominican Republic	7	8	3	15	8	5	36	60
Barbados	9	14	11	20	5	18	23	22
Jamaica	11	22	9	3	7	12	12	34
Puerto Rico	8	7	2	5	6	9	7	10
Cuba	9	6	13	4	7	18	6	14
Haiti	7			3	2	20	6	2
St. Vincent & Grenadines		1		1	1	3	5	
Bahamas	3		1		2	2	4	1
Guadeloupe						1	7	1
Antigua & Barbuda				1		3	3	
Caribbean Netherlands							2	
Dominica				3			2	
Grenada			1		1	1	1	
Cayman Islands		2		1		1	1	
St. Lucia						2	1	2
U.S. Virgin Islands		2	1			1		3
Curaçao	3	1		1	1	2		1
Martinique					1			
Turks & Caicos Islands			1		1			
Aruba	1	1						
British Virgin Islands	1							
Total	97	83	62	75	63	117	144	205